

A Short Note on the Etymology of *Efossus* (Cactaceae)

MAARTEN H. J. VAN DER MEER¹

Abstract—The name *Efossus* is usually explained as an abbreviation of *Echinofossulocactus*, but probably also alludes to Latin *efossus* ‘excavated’.

In 1841, George Lawrence proposed the genus *Echinofossulocactus* for a group of species hitherto mostly included in *Echinocactus* Link & Otto (Lawrence 1841). It quickly faded into oblivion, where it remained until Britton & Rose (1922: 109) revived it by raising *Echinocactus* subgen. *Stenocactus* K.Schum. to generic rank under this name. Several authors protested the resurrection of this obscure genus and no less than three intended replacement names were published: *Brittonrosea* Speg. (1923), *Efossus* Orcutt (1926) and *Stenocactus* (K.Schum.) A.Berger² (1929).

Orcutt’s publication was not available to me, but since other authors invariably explain the name *Efossus* as an abbreviation of *Echinofossulocactus* (Backeberg 1961: 2752; Hunt 1980: 105; Tjaden 1982: 570; Heath 1989: 282; Mottram 2014: 106; Záhora & al. 2018: 47), I presume that this is the etymology given by Orcutt himself. A sneer from Berger (1929: 244) about the ‘awkward name’ that Britton & Rose had ‘exhumed’³, however, points to an additional explanation. One of the possible Latin translations of *exhumed*, which also happens to be cognate with *fossula* ‘furrow’ (the second part in *Echinofossulocactus*), is *efossus*.

¹ Roggekamp 379
NL-2592 VV Den Haag
m@vdm.nu

² If Berger’s publication of this name is considered invalid, it should probably be attributed to Hill (1933: 228). Kreuzinger (1935: 11) attributed it to ‘Fric & Schelle 1932’, but it is unknown what publication this refers to (Zázvorka & Šedivý 1991: 10: ‘Schelle se objevuje u Fričových jmen rodů jako spoluautor s různými roky. ... Co tyto roky znamenají nevíme.’ [‘Schelle appears as co-author of Frič’s generic names with various years. ... We don’t know what these years mean.’])

³ ‘Britton und Rose haben für diese Gruppe den ungefügten Namen *Echinofossulocactus* Lawrence (1841) ausgegraben.’

It is true that Berger wrote this three years after Orcutt, but the metaphor is a fairly obvious one. Berger's remark was quoted by Backeberg & Knuth (1935: 23) as well as by Werdermann (1937: 178). Hunt may have been aware of the wordplay, although he never commented on it. He noted that Britton and Rose had 'duly exhumed' the name after it had come to their attention and concluded the same article with the epitaph 'Hic iacet *Echinofossulocactus*, nomen genericum ignoranter generatum, diu ignoratum, denique *effossum*⁴, nunc denuo *infossum*. R.I.P.' ['Here lies *Echinofossulocactus*, a generic name created in ignorance, unnoticed for a long time, then *exhumed*, now finally *buried*. R.I.P.'] (Hunt 1980: 105, 107, emphases added).

Although there is no direct proof that Orcutt intended this double meaning of the name *Efossus*, it is not likely a coincidence.

Literature

Backeberg C. & Knuth F. M. (1935). *Kaktus-ABC*. Copenhagen: Nordisk Forlag.

https://www.cactuspro.com/biblio_fichiers/pdf/Backeberg/Backeberg_KaktusABC.pdf

Britton N. L. & Rose J. N. (1922). *The Cactaceae. Descriptions and Illustrations of Plants of the Cactus Family. Volume III*. Washington: Press of Gibson Brothers.

https://www.cactuspro.com/biblio_fichiers/pdf/Britton_Rose/Britton_Rose_Cactaceae_3.pdf

Heath P. V. (1989). The Question of *Echinofossulocactus* (Cactaceae). *Taxon* 38(2): 281-288.

https://www.iapt-taxon.org/historic/Congress/IBC_1993/Echino.pdf

Hill. A. W. (1933). *Index Kewensis Plantarum Phanerogamarum; Supplementum 8*.

<https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/133937>

Hunt D. R. (1980). Decent Re-burial for *Echinofossulocactus* Lawr. *Cactus and Succulent Journal of Great Britain* 42(4): 105-107.

https://www.cactuspro.com/biblio_fichiers/pdf/CSJGB/CSJGB-v42_O.pdf

Kreuzinger K. (1935). *Verzeichnis amerikanischer und anderer Sukkulenten mit Revision der Systematik der Kakteen*. Eger [Cheb]: K. Kreuzinger.

https://www.cactuspro.com/biblio_fichiers/pdf/Fric_Kreuzinger/Fric_Kreuzinger_KreuzKat.pdf

⁴ The word, which literally means 'dug out' (*e[x]* + *fossus*), was variantly spelled as *efossus*, *effossus*, *ecfossus* and *exfossus*.

Lawrence G. (1841). Genus IV. *Echinofossulocactus*. Gardener's Magazine and Register of Rural and Domestic Improvement VII: 317-318.

<https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/32384292>

Mottram R. (2014). The Generitaxa of the Cactaceae: An Annotated Index. The Cactician 4: 1-357.

<http://www.crassulaceae.ch/uploads/files/Publications/The%20Cactician/Cactician%204%20HQ-1.pdf>

Spegazzinii C. (1923). Breves notas cactológicas. Anales de la Sociedad Científica Argentina XCVI: 61-74.

<https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/193056>

Tjaden W.L. (1982). (673) Proposal to Conserve 5408 *Stenocactus* (K. Schum.) Berger (1929) over *Echinofossulocactus* Britton & Rose (1922) and Other Generic Names (Cactaceae). Taxon 31(3): 570-573.

Werdermann E. (1937). *Echinofossulocactus*–*Brittonrosea*–*Stenocactus*, welcher Name ist gültig?. Kakteenkunde 1937(12): 177-180.

https://www.cactuspro.com/biblio_fichiers/pdf/Kakteenkunde/Kakteenkunde1937.pdf

Záhora J., Najera Quezada P, Flores Flores J. L. & Morales J. (2018). *Echinofossulocactus* or *Stenocactus*. Xerophilia VII(1): 44-58.

<http://xerophilia.ro/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/xerophilia-2018.12-24-1.pdf>

Zázvorka J. & Šedivý V. (1991). Jména kaktusů A.V. Friče. Aztekia 14: 3-97.

https://www.cactuspro.com/biblio_fichiers/pdf/Aztekia/AztekiaFric.pdf